

HETEROGENEOUS COMPUTING IN SYCL/DPC++ WITH THE ATLAS OFFLINE SOFTWARE

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

ATLAS's software release, Athena is responsible for simulating, triggering, and processing all of the data needed for analyzing the proton-proton collisions produced by the Large Hadron Collider in the center of the ATLAS detector. This is achieved through the correct scheduling and execution of hundreds of "algorithms", with each responsible for a well-defined step of the data processing. All this algorithmic code of ATLAS has been implemented using standard C++, targeting classical CPUs. However now with the advent of more and more computing power coming from non-CPU resources, the ATLAS software has to be updated to be able to target such new style resources. The project is to contribute to the R&D work involved in these developments and to measure the performance of Athena jobs that offload part of their calculations to accelerators using the SYCL/oneAPI/DPC++ programming interface.

ABSTRACT

As the increase in processor performance drops and we've come to see the end of Moore's Law [1], one might rightfully think that the future of computing is parallel. To achieve parallel execution, new hardware components need to be utilized, resulting in heterogeneous architectures. This report provides insights into the utilization of heterogeneous backends, focusing on ATLAS's Offline Software. The seed finding algorithm of the track reconstruction software was implemented in SYCL with DPC++, to offload computations to GPUs. The code successfully ran on diverse architectures, and measurements indicate, that it can provide a performance boost compared to the CPU version of the algorithm.

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1. INTRODUCTION

As the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) is heading towards its Run 3 data-taking, scientists are preparing for the new challenges ahead. After Run 3, the collider is scheduled for another Long Shutdown (LS), the third in the history of the LHC. During the shutdown, the High Luminosity (HL) installation will take place. This upgrade will introduce a baseline instantaneous luminosity of $5 \cdot 10^{34} \text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ and an ultimate achievable luminosity of $7,5 \cdot 10^{34} \text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ [2]. This means an increase in the instantaneous luminosity of the LHC by approximately a factor of five over its initial design (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. The updated project schedule for the High Luminosity LHC upgrade [3] (August 2020).

The HL upgrade will increase the average pile-up (PU) in the recorded events, which is the number of proton-proton collisions or interactions per bunch crossing. During the Run 2 data-taking the ATLAS Experiment recorded an average pile-up ($\langle \mu \rangle$) of 33,7 [3] (see Figure 2). This will increase during the HL phase, to approximately 200 [2]. With the increase of collision event complexity, reconstructing the events becomes more difficult. Focusing on the offline side of the reconstruction, higher PU conditions effectively mean more hits that need to be connected to form particle trajectories.

Another challenge is the search for new exotic particles, such as long-lived Beyond Standard Model (BSM) particles [4]. This often requires special event reconstruction, as decays of long-lived BSM particles typically have larger impact parameters than the constrained limits of the standard reconstruction.

Figure 2. ATLAS Collaboration: Number of Interactions per Crossings. Showing the data taken at $\sqrt{s} = 13\text{TeV}$ from 2015 to 2018 [5].

Either way, these new challenges increase computational complexity and therefore the resources and time needed to carry them out. One of the ideas to tackle this challenge is with the utilization of heterogeneous computing resources. There are already some groups, that managed to show promising results in this area [6].

This report provides additional insights into the utilization of heterogeneous computing resources, focusing on ATLAS's Offline Software. As most of the ATLAS offline reconstruction software is implemented in C++, it is reasonable to use programming interfaces that also rely on C++. One such model is SYCL, a cross-platform abstraction layer, that enables code to be written on heterogeneous processors in standard ISO C++, all in a single-source style [7].

2. TECHNOLOGICAL BACKGROUND

a. The SYCL Specification

SYCL is an open-source specification released and maintained by the Khronos Group. In May 2015, Khronos released the finalized version of SYCL 1.2., which was followed by SYCL 1.2.1. in April 2017, and now the 2020 provisional specification [8].

One of the advantages of SYCL is its single source-model, allowing developers to write host and device code in the same source file. SYCL also allows the usage of standard ISO C++, building on features of C++11, and additional support for C++14 and C++17, such as C++17 Parallel STL [7]. The new provisional 2020 specification is based on C++17, and there are also plans for a 2021 specification that would allow the usage of C++20 features [9]. SYCL does not introduce new keywords, which makes it simple to use, and with the combination of modern C++ features, also powerful.

There are currently several SYCL implementations (see Figure 3), that allow targeting diverse acceleration API back-ends in addition to OpenCL. This means easier portability, which makes SYCL even more appealing.

Besides the support for targeting diverse API back-ends, Intel's DPC++ implementation has several extensions that make it exceptionally powerful. Many of these features were also proposed and will

possibly be accepted in the 2020 specification [10]. Just to name a few among the many, there are reduction tools, explicit memory management (with Unified Shared Memory), sub-groups, and sub-group algorithms.

Figure 3. SYCL Implementations [6]

b. oneAPI and DPC++

DPC++ extensions are part of Intel’s oneAPI toolkit (see Figure 4). Within the toolkit, there are also solutions for AI and data analytics, powerful libraries for deep learning, math, video, and media processing, as well as analysis and debug tools [11]. These products allow targeting diverse architectures, CPUs, GPUs, FPGAs, and other accelerators. With a unified API, developers have an easier job maintaining code. Combined with powerful libraries and language features, efficiency can be highly improved and space for innovation can be made.

As previously mentioned, (see a. The SYCL Specification) DPC++ includes several extensions to SYCL specification, contributed by the community and industry. Just as SYCL, the DPC++ compiler is also open-source, and is built on top of LLVM/Clang.

Figure 4. Intel oneAPI toolkit overview [10]

3. ATLAS TRACKING

The data of a detector readout is stored in raw format. This raw data is then processed, and clusters are formed, and then to each a 3D hit position is assigned.

These hits are also referred to as space points. These hits, from the pixel and strip detectors are used to generate seeds. Seeds are formed of three space points, which allow for a crude identification of a particle, as these three points correspond to a helix, which is the path of a charged particle in a uniform magnetic field [12].

a. Seed generation

Seed generation is limited by many factors, effects such as multiple scattering and impact parameter limitations need to be considered.

Seeding starts with duplet formation of two space points, which are then connected to form triplets if they have a common middle space point and fulfil some other criteria. After some final filtering of the found seed candidates, they are forwarded for later parts of the tracking algorithm.

Figure 5. Seed and track formation of detector hits

Vaguely, this consists of track trajectory prediction, fitting and selection in iterative steps, achieved with a combinatorial Kalman Filter [13]. This starts with the previously reconstructed seeds extended to remaining pixel layers and silicon strips to predict and fit trajectories.

Further details are not discussed here, as the focus of this report is on seed generation. The complexity of the problem is cubic but can be reduced to quadratic due to some restrictions on the impact parameter and the assumption of a helical trajectory. This still makes this step of the algorithm computationally expensive, especially in high intensity events.

It was investigated, how seeding could be implemented as a parallel algorithm, potentially increasing performance. What makes seeding a good candidate for parallelization, is the independent nature of duplet and triplet formation.

4. RESULTS

The complete seeding algorithm was implemented in SYCL with DPC++, which was successfully merged into the Acts Github repository [14]. It is based on the SYCL 1.2.1. specification and extensions from DPC++ such as the Unified Memory Model were used. Therefore, the code can be compiled with Intel's DPC++ compiler.

```
// coordinate transformation middle-top pairs
auto linT = q->submit([&](cl::sycl::handler& h) {
  h.parallel_for<transform_coord_top_kernel>(
    edgesTopNdRange, [=](cl::sycl::nd_item<1> item) {
      auto idx = item.get_global_linear_id();
      if (idx < edgesTop) {
        const auto midSP = deviceMiddleSPs[deviceMidIndPerTop[idx]];
        const auto topSP = deviceTopSPs[deviceIndTop[idx]];

        const auto xM = midSP.x;
        const auto yM = midSP.y;
        const auto zM = midSP.z;
        const auto rM = midSP.r;
        const auto varianceZM = midSP.varZ;
        const auto varianceRM = midSP.varR;
        const auto cosPhiM = xM / rM;
        const auto sinPhiM = yM / rM;
      }
    }
  );
});
```

Figure 6. Code sample from the seed finding algorithm implemented in SYCL. The algorithm does essentially the same, as the CPU version, also keeping naming conventions.

Implementation details and notes on further developments were provided in a subsequent pull request on documentation and inline comments [15]. The documentation explains memory management, how data is indexed and accessed inside kernels as well as the scheduling of kernels. Further notes were left regarding memory management and the last step of the algorithm, namely seed filtering. The current solutions to these are only sub-optimal and seem to be the bottleneck for events with certain complexities. Therefore, in case the algorithm is to be used in the future, these solutions should be reconsidered.

a. Performance measurements

Performance of the code was measured on ttbar Monte-Carlo samples generated for the ATLAS detector. The experimental setup of the machine where the performance of the CPU algorithm compared the SYCL based GPU algorithm was measured is described below.

Figure 7. Performance metrics of SYCL based seed finding algorithm on our experimental setup

Experimental setup:

- CPU: Intel® Core™ i9-9900K Processor (16M Cache, up to 5.00 GHz)
- GPU: Nvidia GeForce RTX 2060 6GB GDDR6

On Figure 7, three plots describe absolute and relative (speed-up) runtime, as well as the agreement of the new algorithm compared the CPU version. According to this, precision remains high, above 99,9% even for the high complexity events. On samples with more than 50 thousand space points (approximately), the GPU algorithm achieves better performance on the experimental setup, which can be read from the middle plot.

b. Other contributions

One of the main advantages of Intel’s DPC++ implementation is its support for diverse architectures. The SYCL version of the seed finding algorithm was tested and ran successfully on several architectures, on OpenCL (Intel Gen9 Integrated Graphics and Intel Gen12 Discrete Graphics) and CUDA backends (Turing and Pascal architectures). These tests confirm that SYCL is indeed successful in utilizing heterogeneous backends.

Furthermore, the project resulted in contribution to the development of the DPC++ compiler, by filing reports about bugs and defect we found during development. Other than that, further possibilities of developments were discussed with Codeplay Software, one of the core supporters of the SYCL specification and maintainers of the ComputeCpp implementation. More details on these subjects can be found in the “official” presentation made on the summer project [16].

5. CONCLUSION

A complete and close to optimal version of the seed finding algorithm was implemented in SYCL with DPC++. The code was compiled and ran on several architectures, which proves the flexibility of SYCL. Performance measurements show that the new algorithm is effective and can provide a performance boost, especially for high intensity events.

One of the directions for future developments is implementing more algorithms in SYCL, possibly starting from the local reconstruction steps. This would allow less memory movement between device and host, which is often the bottleneck with lower intensity events.

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